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Teachers' Characteristics and Attitudes Towards Formative Assessment in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State of Nigeria

Essien, Enobong Jackson (PhD)

**Department of Educational Psychology Guidance & Counselling,
Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt, Nigeria
jacksonenobong40@yahoo.com**

ABSTRACT

The study was carried out to determine Teachers' characteristics and attitudes towards Formative Assessment in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State. Ex-post facto research design was adopted for the study. The population was made up of 6893 Secondary Schools Teachers' in Rivers State. Multi stage sampling was adopted to draw the sample size of three hundred and seventy-eight (378) respondents. Self-structure questionnaires titled Teachers' Attitudes towards Formative Assessment scale" was used to gather data. The instrument was validated by two lecturers in Measurement and Evaluation from Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Port Harcourt. The instrument was pilot tested and the reliability coefficient was determined to be 0.81. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation with 2.50 as criterion mean while hypotheses were tested with one way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and independent sample t-test at 0.05 alpha levels. The findings of the study showed that, there is a significant difference in Teachers' characteristics and attitudes towards Formative Assessment in public secondary schools in the study areas. Recommendations were made which includes that, monitoring and supervision of assessment practice by the teachers should be stepped up by the Ministry of Education in Secondary Schools in the State. This should not be done with the objectives of finding defaulters among the teachers but with the sense of check and balances in putting sanity into the system and also retraining of teachers is necessary to update their knowledge especially those who have poor educational background and those who lack classroom management skills, such training and retraining is very pertinent in achieving educational goals.

Keywords: Teachers Characteristics, Attitudes, Formation Assessment.

INTRODUCTION

In a developing or developed countries of the world, the quality of education and pedagogical output of such country is largely responsible for the overall growth of such nation. For any educational systems to love up to its expectations there are certain importance and key areas that cannot be ignored; they are like the hub and the wheel that drives the system without which there will be no meaningful output. Owen (2005) in Asuk (2021) states that, education is a process of instruction and a way of developing and discipline of the mind to absorb facts and issues as well as cultivating the mental abilities of individual. In other words, the functionality and quality of education depends solely on the educational instrument used (assessment, test and evaluation). Assessment constitutes the central focus in the educational system, it includes the totality of the process of collating information for decision making about the learners, teachers, the instructional process, the curriculum, the schools, educational policies and the society at large (Asuk, 2021). In other dimensions, Essien (2023) states that, assessment provides information about learning that can be used to diagnose learners' strength and needs, provides a basic for instructional placement, inform and guide instruction, motivate and focus learners' attention, provides the basic for learners' evaluation and program effectiveness.

In Nigeria educational system, there are two types of assessment namely; internal and external assessment. The internal assessment includes continuous assessment, terminal and promotion examination otherwise known as teachers made test while external are the junior secondary school certificate conducted by the respective state ministries of education, senior secondary school certificate examination etc. popularly referred to as a standardized test. As with most effective teaching methods and practices, individual teachers have probably used formative assessment throughout history.

Indeed, we could claim Socrates as an early practitioner preparing his students with questions that probed, provoked and used their responses to measure their learning and guide his instructions; this was primarily attributed to formative assessment. Scriven (1967) used formative and summative to indicate difference in both the goals for collecting information and how that information is used. Scriven explained that while a program is in the planning and development stages, it is still malleable and the information gathered from assessment could therefore contribute to change in the program. He called assessment for this purpose of improving “formative” once a program has been created and implemented; scriven argued that assessment could only yield information to determine the program has met its intended goals. Scriven called this final gathering of information as summative.

However, Bloom was one of the first to apply the concepts of formative versus summative to educational assessment helping to lay the foundation for the concept of mastery learning (Bloom, Hasting & Madaus, 1971 in Essien, 2023). The purpose of mastery learning was to ensure that students did not move forward to the next level of learning until they had demonstrated mastery of the learning objectives set for the current level. Formative assessment refers to frequent interactive assessment of students’ progress and understanding of what goes on in the instructional process to identify whether instructional objectives are being achieved from both teachers and pupils’ perspective. Instantly, information about students’ performance is obtained, assessed and immediate feedback given to the students, so that students can be continuously adjusted and improved. Bell and Cowie (2010) posited that, formative assessment measures students’ performances during instruction and usually occurs regularly throughout the instructional process.

The researcher noticed that, some teachers often complain about sacrificing time to assess students during the lesson with the fear that they may not even finished the lesson.

Despite its perceived shortcoming formative assessment delivers information during the instructional process, before the summative assessment which is at the end of the instruction. Both the teachers and the students’ use formative assessment results to make further decision of promoting teaching/learning process. Qualters (2000) defined formative assessment as those activities that are use to improve students’ learning.

Those activities may be graded or ungraded but they provide learners with information that allows them to learn something about their own knowledge, skills, make a change and ultimately improve their learning. To Black and William (2010) argues that once students become independent learners, they develop skills in meta-cognitive which can bring about surprising consequences in terms of learning outcome.

The researcher noticed that, formative assessment encourages students to think more, to develop skills in assessing themselves or their peers and to learn to be collaborative learners. When formative assessment is used within the classroom, teachers may vary in their interpretation and application of the same performance criteria either among themselves or with different students in classes. It allows the teachers to adopt instruction based on results, making modifications and improvements that will produce immediate benefits for students learning. These give the teachers ability to provide constant feedback to the students, while on the order hand, allowing students to be part of the learning processes and to develop self-assessment strategies that will help them with the understanding of their own thought.

Formative Assessment can be done formally often times but not always and are used as a grade in students’ academic record. It includes quizzes, work samples, daily work exist slip and journal. On the other hand, it can also be done in an informal manner. Informal assessment is not used for grading purpose rather they are used to get a quick reference on how students understand a specific topic or lesson. It includes white board demonstration and direct questions to the students (Bell and Cowie, 2010).

Importance of Formative Assessment in Educational System

1. It provides feedback for teachers to modify subsequent learning activities and experiment
2. It identifies and remediate group or individual deficiencies
3. It does not focus in achieving grades rather it helps learners to become aware of any gaps that exist between their desired goal and their current knowledge.
4. It improves student meta-cognitive awareness of how they learn.

Formative Assessment as Students based;

Formative assessment is purposefully directed towards the students;

1. It does not emphasize how teachers deliver instruction rather how students receive that information, how well they understand it and how they apply it.
2. With formative assessment, teachers gather information about their students' progress; learning needs and used this information to make instructional adjustment.
3. It also shows students how to accurately and honestly used self-assessment to improve their own learning, instructional flexibility and students focused on feedback, works together to build confident and motivate learners.

Formative Assessment as Teachers based;

1. It considers each students learning needs and styles and adapt instruction accordingly
2. It tracks individual students' achievement.
3. It designs intentional and objective students' self-assessment
4. It offers students opportunities for improvement

Formative Assessment as Instructional based;

1. Embeds assessment in instructions
2. Guides instructional design
3. Provides a way to align standards, contents and assessment
4. Allow for the purposeful selection of strategies

Formative Assessment as Outcome based;

1. Emphasizes learning outcomes
2. Make goals and standards transparent to students
3. Closes the gap between what student knows and their desired outcomes
4. Provides feedback that is comprehensible, actionable and relevant
5. Provides valuable diagnostics information by generating informative data

The Teachers' quality can be referred to as Teachers' Professionalism; this is the characteristics possessed by the teachers. It can be seen in the knowledge, skills, attitudes and an ability of the teachers to do his/her job. Ekpo, et al. (2021) defined teachers' education as a program of education, research and training of person which empowers them with proficiency and competence to teach at the particular level of education they have been trained for. In the same vein, Ogunyinka, et al. (2015) opined that teachers' education is the professional education of teachers towards attainment of attitudes skills and knowledge considered desirable so as to make them efficient and effective in their work, in accordance with the needs of a given society at any point in time.

However, Mwebaze (2010) comments that, professional teachers have high level of compliance with administration of formative assessment because it provides feedback about students' performance and achievement. To this end, orluwene (2015) asserted that, the primary professional responsibility of the teachers involves desirable behavioral changes in the learners through planned intervention. As it is often in the case of teachers, in collaboration with other educational stake holders such as; curriculum planners, examination bodies, international donor organization and civil society organization, break down the broad educational aims into smaller classroom instructional objectives. Torrance (2012) stated that, irrespective of who make decision regarding the information provided from formative assessment, the major initiator and users is the teachers. It is for this purpose that attempts at improving teachers' formative assessment practice should be grounded in empirical evidence and on of such evidence entails ascertaining their attitudes towards formative assessment .It is imperative to note that, the quality of teachers is a predictor of academic performance which is a sign of quality education. The most important agent of change in the classroom is the teachers. In other dimension, Ekpo, et al. (2021) added that, in any societies around the world, teachers are looked upon as the individuals who can bring about positive change in the live of people. Kent (2004) reiterated that, experienced acquire by teachers differs significantly based on their years of teaching; they are responsible for the progress of any society, they prepare the young generation, their level of knowledge devotion and determines the future of the society.

The researcher added that, professional teachers have positive attitudes toward Formative Assessment than Non-Professional counterpart because on the spot, instructions are being assessed, on the other hand, noticing the worth of the teachers; teacher as someone who has undergone some approved professional training in teacher education capable of impacting knowledge attitude and skills to learners.

This concept of attitudes as conceptualized by Kpolovie, et al, (2014) refers to sum total of an individual positive and negative predisposition or mental state of preparation for action or in response to a social object. In the other dimension Kpolovie and Iderima (2016) added that, an attitude signifies individual's characteristics ways of thinking, feeling and behaving.

An attitude is an evaluation of a person's positive and negative predisposition towards an object being or thing. It is sum total of Man's inclination and feelings prejudice or bias, preconceived notion, ideas, fear, threat and conviction about any specific topic. Jones (2002) sees attitudes as a function of what people think and what they feel. That is, attitude is the product of related beliefs and values. If ones believe that, his teacher is consultative and he values consultative. One might have a favorable attitude towards the teacher. Nwanze (2015) defined attitude as an individual's prevailing tendency to respond favorably or unfavorably to an object (person, or group of people, institution or event). It can be either positive or negative; Kreither and Kinieki (2007) added that, there are three components of attitude; affective, cognitive and behavioral. The feeling or an emotion one has about an object or situation; cognitive is the idea or belief one has about a situation while the behavioral reflects how one intends to act or behave toward someone or things. A positive attitude is a key to maintaining a positive classroom environment.

Statement of the Problem

In our public secondary schools today, some teachers' exhibit poor attitude toward formative assessment, these poor attitudes over the year has been attributed to different factors such as; poor salaries structure, lack of teachers' knowledge on the subject matter, insufficient qualified and professional teachers and lack of motivation to name the least. This has led to increase in work errors, inability to cover scheme of work, not attending to lessons promptly, problem of choice of appropriate teaching method, hostility towards students and colleagues. When this happens, students view schools as boring and uninteresting. In another dimension, experience revealed that most teachers assumed that their responsibilities are just that of teaching students and not to assess them. It is therefore imperative that how teachers view this very important part of assessment should be of interest for empirical investigation.

Purpose of the study

The aim of the study was to examine teachers' characteristic and attitude toward formative assessment in public secondary schools in Rivers State. The study sought;

- (1) To examine the extent to which years of teaching experience differ from teachers' attitude toward formative assessment
- (2) To examine the extent to which educational qualification differ from the teachers' attitude toward formative assessment.

Research Question

The following research questions guided the study;

- (1) To what extent does Teachers' attitude toward Formative Assessment differ based on years of teaching experience?
- (2) To what extent does teachers' attitude toward formative assessment differ based on educational qualifications?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study;

- (1) There is no significant different between teachers with different years of teaching experience and attitude toward formative assessment
- (2) These is no significant difference between teachers with different educational qualifications and attitude toward formative assessment

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted Ex-post facto research design. Ex-post facto research design is that which seem to identify the extent to which a set of variable or characteristics relate to a dependable variable without any deliberate attempts at manipulating any of the variables by the researcher.

Nwankwo (1999) in Kpolovie (2010) defined Ex- post facto research design as a design which involves collecting and analyzing data from some variables which are already in place (without

manipulating any of them) in order to find out how some of them influenced or are related to other variables. The state has 286 government owned secondary schools with a population of 6893 teachers, during 2022/2023 academic session (Source Rivers State Ministry of Education, 2024). Multi- Stage sampling was adopted to draw the sample size of 378 respondents. Self-structured questionnaires titled “**Teachers’ Attitudes toward Formative Assessment scale**” (TATFAS) was used to gather data. To facilitate data analysis and establishment of the validity of the instrument. The instrument was subjected to experts’ for scrutiny to make sure the instrument measures what it intended to measure. The instrument yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.81 through test re- test method. Four-point rating scale was used to weigh; Very High Extent (4) High extent (3), Low Extent. (2) And very Low Extent (1). Mean and Standard deviation were used to answer research questions while independent sample t-test and one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significant.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *To what extent does a Teachers attitude toward Formation Assessment differ based on years of teaching experiences?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard deviation of Teachers attitude towards Formative Assessment based on years of teaching experience

S/No	STATEMENT	1-10			11-20			21 & above		
		X	SD	RMK	X	SD	RMK	X	SD	RMK
1	Experience acquired by teachers increases their effectiveness during Formative Assessment	2.54	0.15	HE	2.96	0.23	HE	3.25	0.27	HE
2	Experience Teachers inculcate interest and concentration of the students during formative assessment administration	2.54	0.15	HE	2.97	0.23	HE	3.29	0.28	HE
3	Students knows their teacher’s area of interest through formative assessment	2.53	0.15	HE	2.98	0.23	HE	3.02	0.25	HE
4	Ability of experienced teachers to construct test with psychometric properties (validity, reliability & usability facilitate students understanding of the lesson)	2.57	0.18	HE	3.12	0.24	HE	3.10	0.26	HE
5	Knowledge of innovation by experienced teachers during teaching/learning facilitate students understanding of the lesson	2.54	0.15	HE	2.21	0.22	LE	3.06	0.26	HE
	Grand mean (X) and Standard Deviation (SD)	2.54	0.16	HE	2.85	0.23	HE	3.14	0.26	HE

Result from table 1 above shows that teachers between 1-10 years experienced indicated high extent in all the items with a grand mean of (X=2.54), 11-20 years experienced indicated low extent in item 5 with a grand mean of (X=2.21) and 21 years and above had the highest mean of (X=3.14)

respectively. The conclusion which could be drawn from these results is that, teachers with different years of teaching experience had different attitudes towards formative assessment in public secondary schools in Rivers state.

Research Question 2: *To what extent does teachers' attitude towards formative assessment differ based on educational qualifications?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Teachers Attitudes towards Formative Assessment based on Educational Qualification

S/No	Statement	Professional Teachers		Non-Professional teachers			
		X	SD	RMK	X	SD	RMK
6	I am excited to apply formative assessment during teaching/learning process.	3.17	0.15	HE	2.13	0.21	LE
7	Formative Assessment makes teaching/learning process boring for teachers	3.27	0.13	HE	2.90	0.22	HE
8	I don't provide corrective feedback because of the number of students involved in my class	3.20	0.13	HE	2.32	0.21	LE
9	The role for Administration of Formative Assessment should not be assigned to Professional alone	3.19	0.15	HE	2.12	0.12	LE
10	Formative Assessment increases Teachers' effectiveness	3.16	0.14	HE	2.64	0.22	HE
	Grand Mean (X) and Standard Deviation	3.20	0.59	HE	2.42	0.21	LE

Field Work 2023 (HE=high extent, LE=low extent, RMK=remark).

Result from Table 2 showed that, Professional Teachers indicated high extent in all the items with a grand mean of (X=3.20) while the Non-Professional counterpart indicated low extent in items 6, 8, and 9 with a grand mean of (X=2.42) which is below the Criterion mean of 2.50. This implies that Professional Teachers have different attitudes towards Formative Assessment than Non-Professional Counterparts.

Table 3: One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on Teacher's years of teaching experience towards Formative Assessment.

Source of Variance	Sum of Square	DF	Mean Square	F-GS	F-Crit	Decision
Between Square	10346.62	2	5173.31	22.01	5.39	Rejected
Within Square	8462.41	36	235.067			
Total	18809.03	38				

Table 3 Above depicts the ANOVA Summary of the difference in the years of teaching experience and attitudes toward Formative Assessment. Between group the sum of Square was 10346.62 with 2 degree of freedom and the mean square of 5173.31. For within group, the sum of square was 8462.41 with 36 degrees of freedom with means square of 235.067. The total has 18809.03 with 38 degrees of freedom. F-cal. of 22.01 is greater than F- crit. of 5.39. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that, there is a significant difference in Teachers attitudes towards Formative Assessment in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: t-test analysis of Teachers attitudes towards Formative Assessment based on Educational Qualification.

Categories	N	X	SD	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Professional Teachers	205	3.20	0.59	376	19.02	1.960	Rejected
Non-Professional Teachers	173	2.42	0.21				

Table 4 above shows that, professional teachers (N=205) with a mean value of (X=3.20) and Standard Deviation of (SD=0.59) while Non-Professional counterpart (N=173) with a mean value of (X=2.42) and Standard Deviation of (SD=0.21). When subjected to Independent Sample t-test yielded a t-cal value of 19.02, df = 376, t-crit. 1.960. Since the t-cal value of 19.02 is greater than the t-crit. of 1.960. The null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there is a significant difference between Professional and Non-Professional Teachers and their attitudes towards Formative Assessment in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The findings in research question one showed years of teaching experience and teachers' attitudes toward formative assessment in public secondary schools in Rivers State. The findings of this study align with Kent (2004) who comments that, experience acquired by teachers differs significantly based on their years of teaching. He added that, experience acquired by teachers would enable the utilization of instructions, information assessments and feedback given to the learners, so that learners will be continuously adjusted.

The findings in research question two showed educational qualifications differ from teachers' attitudes toward Formative Assessment in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers state. The finding was in line with Nwabueze (2010) who comments that, professional teachers shows high level of compliance with formative assessment because it provides feedback about students' performance and achievement. He reiterated that; professional teachers differ significantly than non-professional counterpart. Therefore, teachers rely on assessment in order to monitor the student's academic performance and progress; assessment becomes an Interaction between the teachers and the students with the teachers continually seeking to understand what the students can do, how a student is able to do it and then using this information appropriately. He added that, teachers need to have professional Knowledge and Competency that would assist them in achieving their proficiency in the field. The researcher added that, the primary professional responsibility of the teachers involves desirable behavioral changes in the learners through planned intervention.

CONCLUSION

The relevance of formative assessment for qualitative education cannot be overemphasized because it is a significant path that tailors activities of both the teachers and the learners on the corrective feedback in teaching learning process. From the findings of this study, there is significant difference in teachers' characteristic and attitudes toward formative assessment in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made;

1. Monitoring and supervision of assessment practices by teachers should be stepped up by the ministry of education in secondary schools in the state. This should not be done with objective of finding defaulters among the teachers, but with sense of "check and balances" in putting sanity into the system.

- Retraining of teachers is necessary to updating their knowledge especially those which have poor educational background, those who lack classroom management skills, such training and retraining is very pertinent in archiving educational goals.

REFERENCES

- Asuks U.W (2021). The Challenges of Test, Assessment and Evaluation in the 21st century in Nigeria Educational System. *Journal of Education & Society 11(3)*, 1755 - 1767
- Black P.& William, D. (2010). Assessment and Classroom learning. *Journal of Assessment in education 11(2)* 49 – 65.
- Bell, B & Cowie, B. (2010) Characteristics of Formative Assessment. *Journal of Empirical studies in education 1 (14)* 536 – 544.
- Bloom, B.S, Hasting, T. & Madaus, U. (1971). *Handbook of Formation and Summative Evaluation of Students learning*. MC Gra – Hil.
- Cowie, H. (2010) Formative Assessment. Retrieved from www.learning.org/ip/pages/5212.
- Ekpo, E.& Onwuchuruba,B.U(2021).Teachers Professionalism: Avertible Tools for Effective Performance of Public Primary School Pupils in Rivers State *Journal of Education and Society 11(3)*, 2044-2025.
- Essien, E.J.(2023).Teachers Perception on the Challenges in the Implementation of School Based Assessment in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State *Journal of Innovative Education Research 11(3)*, 68-75.
- Jone, w. (2002) *Making a Difference through Teaching* Black Collegian
- Kent,A.M.(2004) Improving Teachers Quality Through Professional Development.*Journal of Education 124 (3)*, 437-435.
- Kpoluvie, P.J., Joe, A.Sokoto, T. (2014), Academic Achievement Predictive: Role of Internet in learning Attitudes Toward Schools. <http://www.arc.journal.org/pdfs/ijhsse/101/10-18pdf>.
- Kreither, R& Kinieki, A(2007) *Organization of Behavior*. McRaw- Hill Ryerson publisher.
- Nwebaza, M. (2010). Continuous Assessment and Students Performance in A Level secondary School in Masaki District. Unpolished M. Ed Dissertation Makerere University Kampala.
- Nwanze, U. (2015) *Teaching Skills. Hand Book For Trainer Teachers*. Crystal Publisher.
- Orluwene, G. (2015). *Fundamental of Testing and Non-testing Tools in Educational Psychology*. Harey Publishers.
- Onyenyinka, E.K. & Okeke, T. (2015).Teachers Education and Development. Research gate <https://www.researchgate.net>.
- Owen, A.E (2002). *Introduction to Psychology of Education*. Midland press ltd.
- Qualters, D.M.(2000). *Using Classroom Assessment Data to Improve Students learning*. North Eastern University press.
- Scriven, M (1967).Methodology of Evaluation.American Education Research Association. Monograph Series on Evaluation No.1.
- Tarrance, H. (2012) Formative Assessment Some Theoretical Problems and Empirical Questions. *Cambridge Journal of Education 23(3)* 333-343.